

The multi-faceted role of TGFBR3 deregulation in oral cancer progression

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Abstract:

TGF- β type III receptor (TGFBR3), a co-receptor for TGF- β family members, is required for the high-affinity binding of ligands to their receptors to initiate their cellular function. More and more studies showed an opposing role of TGFBR3, tumor suppressor or oncogene, in different cancer types. However, the exact role of TGFBR3 and the responsible mechanism in oral cancer remains to be characterized. By using in silico analysis, immunohistochemical staining and real-time PCR, we found a down-regulation of TGFBR3 in oral cancer tissues when compared to their adjacent normal counterparts. Low TGFBR3 expression patients tend to have poor clinical outcome compared with high expression patients. Furthermore, promoter methylation and TGF- β 1 expression were involved in the decrease of TGFBR3 expression. To examine the role of TGFBR3 in oral cancer cells, we not only stably expressed shRNAs specific to TGFBR3 but also overexpressed TGFBR3, respectively, in oral cancer cells. TGFBR3 overexpression decreased cell migration, invasion and metastasis. Oral cancer cells with depleted TGFBR3 expression exhibited increased migration and invasion compared with control cells. Besides, TGFBR3 overexpression attenuated TGF- β 1 stimulated SMAD2/3 phosphorylation and reduced SMAD4 nuclear translocation suggesting a negative role of TGFBR3 for canonical TGF- β signaling. The cytoplasmic domain of TGFBR3 mediates its suppressive effect through GIPC1, a scaffolding protein. TCGA head and neck cancer database analysis also showed that the concordant reduction of GIPC1 and TGFBR3 expression significantly reduced patient clinical outcome, suggesting that TGFBR3 and GIPC1 functions in the same signaling axis. Moreover, the conditioned medium from TGFBR3 overexpressing cancer cells also harbored tumor suppressive effects both on tumor cells and stromal cells. (Figure 1). This study should facilitate the possibility of using TGFBR3 mediated tumor suppression for oral cancer treatment.

Keywords:

Oral cancer, tumor microenvironment, TGF- β , TGFBR3, GIPC1, angiogenin.

Figure 1: Illustrating the proposed mechanism of TGFBR3-mediated tumor suppressive effects in oral cancer.

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Effects of Pinostilbene Hydrate on human nasopharyngeal carcinoma migration through regulating matrix metalloproteinase-2 expression and MAPK pathway

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Abstract:

Introduction: Nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC) is uncommon in western countries, it is endemic in Southeast Asia and Southern China. Unfortunately, due to the difficulty of early detection, about 70% of patients present with locoregionally advanced disease at diagnosis. Therefore, novel molecular therapeutic targets are being extensively researched. Pinostilbene Hydrate (PSH) has been demonstrated possesses several biological effects, such as anti-inflammatory, anti-tumor, and anti-oxidant. However, the detailed effects of PSH on human nasopharyngeal cancer cell migration and the underlying mechanisms remain unclear.

Materials and method: Cell viability was examined by MTT assay, whereas cell motility was measured by migration, invasion and wound healing assays. Zymography assay and Western blot was used to analyze matrix metalloproteinase-2 (MMP-2) protein activity, protein level and mitogen-activated protein kinase (MAPK) pathway in NPC cells.

Results and discussion: In this study, we demonstrate that PSH attenuated NPC-BM cell migration and invasion in a dose-dependent manner. The anti-metastatic activity of PSH was downregulated by MMP-2 protein activity and protein expression in NPC-BM cells. PSH did inhibit the effects of MMP-2 by reducing the activation of mitogen-activated protein kinases (MAPKs).

Conclusion: These results demonstrate that Pinostilbene Hydrate (PSH) may be a potent adjuvant therapeutic agent in the prevention of human nasopharyngeal carcinoma.

Keywords:

Nasopharyngeal carcinoma, Pinostilbene hydrate, MMP-2, migration, MAPK pathway.

Figure 1: Effects of Pinostilbene hydrate (PSH) on the Viability of human nasopharyngeal carcinoma cells. (A) Chemical structure of Pinostilbene hydrate (PSH). (B) NPC-BM cell line treat with different concentrations (0, 20, 40 and 80 μM) of PSH for 24 h, and the cell viability was determined by MTT assay. The values represented the means ± SD of at least three independent experiments. *P<0.05, compared with the control group.

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Highly specific in-vivo gene delivery for p53-mediated apoptosis and genetic photodynamic therapies of tumour

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Abstract:

Anti-cancer therapies are often compromised by non-specific effects and challenged by tumour environments' inherent physico-chemical and biological characteristics. Often, therapeutic effect can be increased by addressing multiple parameters simultaneously. The mutation and dysfunction of protein 53 (p53) has been associated with over 50% of human cancers. Mutant p53 not only loses tumour suppressive abilities, but additionally leads to promotion of tumourigenesis. Here we report on exploiting extravasation due to inherent vascular leakiness for delivery of a pH sensitive polymer carrier. Tumors' acidic microenvironment instigates a charge reversal that promotes cellular internalization where endosomes destabilize and gene delivery is achieved. We assess our carrier with an aggressive non-small cell lung carcinoma (NSCLC) in-vivo model and achieve greater than 30% transfection efficiency via systemic delivery. Rejuvenation of the p53 apoptotic pathway as well as expression of Killer Red protein for sensitization in photodynamic therapy (PDT) is accomplished (Figure 1). A single administration greatly suppresses tumour growth and extends median animal survival from 28 days in control subjects to 68 days. Such a carrier is highly versatile in its loading as well as effective in being responsive to the 'targeted' tumour tissue micro-environment from systemic administration. In the present study, we simultaneously rejuvenated the p53-mediated apoptosis signaling pathway and enabled photo-induced ROS generation; effectively suppressing tumour growth of an aggressive human NSCLC cell line (H1299) in athymic BALB/c nude mice. The carrier has capacity for multiple payloads for greater therapeutic response where inter-individual variability can compromise efficacy.

Keywords:

p53, tumor microenvironment, nanoparticle, Killer Red, photo-dynamic therapy.

Figure 1: A schematic representation of the gene loaded carrier. Its biocompatible, contracted, negatively charged form circulates freely in a passive form until extravasation into tumour tissue characterized by lowered pH. Tumour acidosis switches the carriers charge to enhance cellular interaction and uptake. Protonation of the carriers' amino groups leads to distention of the polymer chains, dilation and expulsion of payloads. Here, p53 and KillerRed genes transfect tumour cells. p53 triggers apoptosis while illumination of KillerRed protein generates ROS and subsequent intracellular damage, further promoting cell apoptosis.

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Remote Control of Light-Triggered Virotherapy

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Abstract:

Clinical virotherapy has been successfully approved for use in cancer treatment by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA), however a number of improvements are still sought to more broadly develop virotherapy. A particular challenge is to administer viral therapy systemically and overcome limitations in intra-tumoral injection, especially for complex tumor within sensitive organs. To achieve this however, a technique is required that delivers the virus to tumor before the body's natural self defense eradicates the virus prematurely. Here we show that recombinant AAV serotype 2 (AAV2) chemically conjugated with iron oxide nanoparticles (~5 nm) have remarkable ability to be remotely guided under magnetic field. Transduction is achieved with micro scale precision. Furthermore, a gene for production of the photosensitive protein KillerRed was introduced into the AAV2 genome to enable photo-dynamic therapy (PDT); or light-triggered virotherapy (Figure 1). In vivo experiments revealed that magnetic guidance of "ironized" AAV2-KillerRed injected by tail vein in conjunction with PDT significantly decreases the tumor growth via apoptosis. This proof-of-principle demonstrates guided and highly localized micro-scale, light-triggered virotherapy. There are several distinguishing features of our Ironized AAV2, such as targeted delivery, light-triggered activation of virotherapy, lack of recombination and genomic integration, and strong pre-clinical safety record, that define potential advantages of this concept. Furthermore, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) instruments can be applied to create pulsed magnetic field gradients in desired direction, and it may provide the prospect of shaping the accumulation within an internal 3D volume.

Keywords:

Virotherapy, virus particle, nanoparticle, micro-transduction, photo-dynamic therapy.

Figure 1: Concept of a remotely directed Ironized virus by a single tail vein injection for micro-virotherapy. Ironized AAV2 rapidly accumulates in the target tumor site when directed with magnetic field-enforced delivery. Here, KillerRed is expressed by tumor cells infected by AAV2-KillerRed. Light triggers virotherapy. Illumination of KillerRed protein generates ROS and subsequent intracellular damage, promoting cell death.

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Study of the influence of steroids on the acquisition of pro-tumour properties of carcinoma of the nasopharynx in Algerian patients

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Abstract:

The nasopharyngeal carcinoma (NPC) is primarily associated with a genetic and environmental etiology involving the Epstein-Barr virus, a hormonal component to susceptibility or to carcinogenesis mechanisms is not excluded. It is known that NPC affects men about 2 to 3 times more than women in endemic countries.

In Algerian patients with NPC (n = 4) and healthy subjects (n = 4), we are interested in the study of the steroid hormones synthesis and cortisol during NPC within the variations in oxidative, nitrosative stress and the acquisition of a gelatinolytic activity.

The results showed high levels of NO produced by patients ((34.7 $\mu\text{M} \pm 19.92$) vs. (53.15 $\mu\text{M} \pm 26.64$)) this was found to be significantly elevated in patients with low sex hormone levels, in contrast to cortisol, which demonstrates an increase in the correlation with low NO levels (r = 0,123 vs. r = 0.06), and was associated with a reduction in catalase mediated antioxidant activity (r = 0.04 vs. r = -0.64). We observed the existence of a positive correlation between the synthesis levels of oestrogen, progesterone and cortisol on the acquisition of MMP9 activity. The variations of testosterone synthesis could not be associated in MMP9 activity.

In conclusion, our results confirm that the development of NPC is accompanied by a strong production of NO and suggest the presence of a hormonal contribution to this process, which cannot be ruled out. Indeed, our work suggests a probable cross contribution of cortisol and progesterone in the acquisition of expression and activation of MMP9 involved in the acquisition of metastatic capabilities.

Keywords:

Nitric oxide. MMP. Nasopharyngeal carcinoma. Inflammation. Catalase Activity. Steroids. Oestrogen. Progesterone. Testosterone. Cortisol.

Chemosensitizing Effects of Marine Astaxanthin on the Anticancer Activity of Doxorubicin in Tumor Bearing Mice.

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Abstract:

Background and Objectives: Doxorubicin is an efficient antineoplastic drug but its clinical usefulness is limited by its serious adverse effects such as cardiotoxicity. The main objective of this research was to investigate whether natural marine astaxanthin could chemosensitize the Ehrlich ascites carcinoma cells to the anti-tumor effect of doxorubicin.

Materials and Methods: Survival of Ehrlich ascites carcinoma bearing mice was used as model to evaluate the chemosensitizing effect of astaxanthin to doxorubicin cytotoxicity. After treatment with doxorubicin and/or astaxanthin, doxorubicin uptake was measured by spectrofluorometric assay, apoptosis and the cell cycle phase distribution were determined by flow cytometer analysis and P53 gene expression was also studied in the EAC cells

Results : Treatment of tumor bearing mice with doxorubicin showed a significant increase in the mean survival time to 32.5 days with 30 % long-term survivor. Treatment of the tumor-bearing animals with astaxanthin and doxorubicin showed a significant increase in the mean survival time to 41.1 days with 80% long-term survivor. Doxorubicin cellular uptake was increased significantly after astaxanthin treatment. Moreover, astaxanthin treatment dramatically increased the early apoptosis and G2/M phase accumulation after addition to doxorubicin. P53 gene expression was up regulated after doxorubicin treatment; moreover addition of astaxanthin synergized the action of doxorubicin where p53 gene expression was highly unregulated

Conclusion : The present study concluded that the marine astaxanthin potentiate the cytotoxic activity of doxorubicin against the growth of mammary tumor cells in vivo through accumulation of the tumor cells in G2/M phase , induction of apoptosis and up regulation of the tumor suppressor p53 gene expression.

Repurposing antibiotics inducing mitochondrial dysfunction for cancer treatment

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Abstract:

Recently we have shown that a subpopulation of cancer stem cells (CSC) share common qualities with chemo resistant cancer cells (CRCC). Using subsets of cells representing triple negative breast cancer (TNBC) we identified similar metabolic signatures between CSC and CRCC suggesting mitochondria involvement in the cancer cell energy production. On the other hand, the accumulated evidence indicates that several bactericidal antibiotics may effectively induce mitochondrial dysfunction (MDF) and suppress the growth of cancer cells. Thus, treatment of cancer with specific antibiotics may appear as a novel anticancer strategy. To that end, we have studied the effects of antibiotics targeting mitoribosomes and validated several of them in in-vitro and in vivo models of TNBC. In addition, we demonstrated that specific antibiotics were able to discriminate CSC and CRCC from the corresponding parental cancer cells. This suggests that some ant bactericidal antibiotics serving as MDF-inducing drugs can suppress cancer relapse. In order to avoid autophagy (mitophagy) as part of a survival pathway in cancer cells treated with MDF-inducers, antibiotics were administered concomitantly with the autophagy blockers. Our results revealed that specific bactericidal antibiotics used in combination with an autophagy blocker suppress cancer cell proliferation, discriminate CSC and CRCC from parental cancer cells and decrease tumor growth. Such drugs can be repurposed as part of the multitarget anticancer therapy.

Direct-acting antivirals and hepatocellular carcinoma: An Ongoing Debate

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Abstract:

Introduction and aim :

Direct antiviral agents (DAAs) represents a revolution in the treatment of chronic hepatitis C virus (HCV) infection. Due to a more favorable efficacy and safety profile, special populations such as patients with decompensated cirrhosis who were long excluded from treatment with interferon (INF) based regimens.

Over the past decade, several studies have evaluated the role of SVR in preventing hepatic decompensation and reducing the risk of occurrence and recurrence of HCC in HCV cirrhotic patients. Studies from the IFN era taught us that HCV eradication reduces the risk of HCC development even in non-responders because interferon is known by its antiproliferative and anti-fibrotic effect. On the contrary, the impact of DAAs on liver cancer occurrence and recurrence seems to be controversial. The topic became particularly important after publication of two papers from Spain and Italy that suggested a potential increase in the occurrence and recurrence rates of HCC in patients treated with DAAs. Other studies have recently described a potential unexpected recurrence of HCC in DAA treated patients. These reports had generated a controversial debate and had been followed by other publications that doubted such increased risk.

The controversies arise from the heterogeneity of populations, variations in the inclusion and exclusion criteria for each study, the follow up time, the time points used to analyse the occurrence and recurrence rates, and so on.

The debate in the scientific community is still ongoing. So, the aim of this presentation is to analyse the current data concerning the occurrence and recurrence of HCC after DAA treatment and to present our study that compared tumor behavior of HCC after HCV treatment by DAAs with non-DAAs-treated patients.

Patients and Methods:

This case control study includes 89 patients with HCV-related HCC who received generic DAAs and all non-DAA treated patients with HCC who presented to our clinic during the same period (207). Patient and tumor characteristics, treatment types and outcome were compared between the two groups.

Results :

We found that those who received DAAs showed a significantly higher serum α -fetoprotein ($P=0.02$), a more infiltrative HCC pattern, higher incidence of portal vein thrombosis and lymphadenopathy ($P=0.03$ and 0.03 , respectively) when compared with non-DAAs-treated patients. These factors significantly affected the response to HCC management ($P=0.03$). Incidence of complete responses were 47.2 and 49.8% for the DAAs group and non DAAs group, respectively, whereas incomplete responses were 12.4 and 25.1%, respectively. Supportive treatment was applied to 40.4% in the DAAs group and 25.1% in the non DAAs group II.

Conclusion:

The debate of HCC/ DAAs relation is still ongoing. Our study showed that HCC behavior was more aggressive in DAA-treated patients regarding portal vein thrombosis, malignant lymphadenopathy, and HCC imaging characteristics, which affected the chance of ablation and the treatment response

Identification of microRNA expression in sentinel lymph nodes from patients with breast cancer via RNA sequencing for diagnostic accuracy

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Abstract:

Purpose: Sentinel lymph node (SLN) property assessment (with or without metastasis) is important while deciding the surgery for breast cancer; however, the current diagnosis of SLN metastasis remains to be studied. MicroRNAs (miRNAs) have been previously confirmed as a molecular marker for the diagnosis, development, and prognosis of tumours. However, the detailed role of miRNAs in the diagnosis of SLN metastasis has not been reported.

Methods: In this study, to explore the potential use of miRNAs in the diagnosis of SLN, RNA sequencing (RNA-seq) and quantitative real-time polymerase chain reaction (qRT-PCR) were used to compare the expression profiles of miRNAs in patients with breast cancer with or without SLN metastasis.

Results: RNA-seq results revealed that 1993 miRNAs were differentially expressed in patients with breast cancer with SLN metastasis. Among these miRNAs, 1960 were up-regulated and 33 were down-regulated. Gene Ontology and Kyoto Encyclopaedia of Genes and Genomes pathway enrichment analyses revealed that these differentially expressed miRNAs were associated with tumor growth and metastasis and were predicted to regulate a series of tumorigenesis and metastasis genes. In particular, the most differentially expressed miRNAs were validated by qRT-PCR, such that miR-200a-3p and miR-96-5p were up-regulated and miR-1-3p and miR-486-3p were down-regulated in patients with breast cancer with SLN metastasis.

Conclusions: These findings suggested the association of miRNAs with SLN metastasis and that miRNAs function as biomarkers in the therapy of choice and disease prognosis.

References:

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Jumonji histone demethylases drive transcriptional reprogramming in cancer

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Abstract:

Lysine histone demethylases (KDMs) of the Jumonji family are highly upregulated in multiple solid and hematological malignancies and drive oncogenic gene expression patterns. We have uncovered novel roles of Jumonji KDM enzymes in mediating transcriptional reprogramming during the development of resistance to chemotherapy and in enhancing DNA repair in response to radiation. We will present data using both genetic and pharmacological approaches to block the activities of Jumonji demethylases in cells and in vivo. Our findings strongly suggest that inhibition of enzymatic activity is an effective strategy to treat chemoresistant tumors and to prevent the development of drug resistance. Furthermore, we have identified a role for Jumonji enzymes of the Jarid subfamily in DNA repair, by their modulation of H3K4 methylation at sites of DNA damage. In this context, we will report on the radio sensitizing effects of Jarid inhibition in radiation resistant cancer cells and tumors in vivo. Validation of our findings in human populations will also be presented. Our work opens a new paradigm in our mechanistic understanding of how histone demethylases mediate drug and radiation resistance and offers a therapeutic strategy to overcome these obstacles.

Guggulsterone as an anti-inflammatory agent in regulating prostate specific tumor suppressor NKX3.1.

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Abstract:

Research on guggulsterone were mostly concerned with the action of GS as hypolipidemic agent, its interaction with various nuclear and steroid receptors followed by revelation of its anticancer activities in various tumors. The fact that GS is anti-inflammatory as well as targets steroid receptors, accelerates the belief about the role of GS in hormone dependent tumors. Since prostate cancer became a good model to study GS mediated apoptosis. Majority of the studies were carried out on PC3 and DU145 cells as model system for castration resistant prostate Cancer (CRPCa). As a matter of fact these cell line have negligible expression of androgen receptor, as opposed to clinical scenario were 70% of cases maintains AR expression and activity in absence of hormone. Therefore, the information about the effects of GS on AR positive but androgen independent i.e. CRPCa is poorly documented. In this project we intended to examine the effect of GS on CRPCa cell lines. One of the earliest events in PCa initiation is inflammatory cytokines mediated loss of NKX3.1 protein. Given the importance of NKX3.1 expression in PCa as well as the role of GS in cytokine dependent signalling, we aimed to determine whether the GS controls NKX3.1 expression and stability.

Whether canonical NF-kB signalling plays a role for initiation and progression of prostate cancer (PCa) is still a matter of debate. For instance, a class of PCa cell lines (PC3 and DU-145) with low AR expression depend on constitutive IKK and NF-kB activity and enhanced nuclear localization of NF-kB was observed in PCa samples. However, the majority of PCa depend on the activity of the androgen receptor (AR) and the role of NF-kB in these PCa remains unclear. This prompted us to analyze the role of canonical NF-kB signalling in AR expressing PCa cell lines. Inhibition of NF-kB by the pharmacological IKK inhibitor BMS345541 attenuated proliferation and induced apoptosis in a panel of PCa cell lines. Furthermore, AR activity and target gene expression was distinctively reduced while AR protein levels remained unaltered upon BMS345541 treatment. Similar effects on PCa cell proliferation and AR target gene expression were observed particularly after siRNA-mediated knockdown of IKK1. Further biochemical analysis of the AR signalling pathway revealed a reduced nuclear translocation of AR by BMS345541 treatment. In accordance, overexpression of IKK1 augmented the hormone-induced nuclear translocation of AR in COS7 cells and IKK1 increased AR activity in LNCaP cells. Finally, reduced *in vivo* AR phosphorylation after BMS345541 treatment and *in vitro* AR phosphorylation by IKK1 or IKK2 imply that AR constitutes a novel IKK target. Taken together, our data suggest that IKK1 affects the activity of AR possibly by phosphorylation-dependent augmentation of its nuclear translocation.

References:

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Anti-proliferative effect of potential LSD1/CoREST inhibitors based on molecular dynamics model derived from its interaction with tetrahydrofolate cofactor

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Abstract:

Targeting cancer through epigenetics is a recent era, where a specific gene is manipulated without destroying it. Lysine-specific demethylase 1 (LSD1) is one of the enzymes that are associated with chromatin for post-translational modifications, where it demethylates lysine amino acid in the chromatin H3 tail. LSD1 is associated with its corepressor protein CoREST, and utilises tetrahydrofolate as a cofactor to accept CH₂ from the demethylation process. Many studies showed that inhibiting LSD1 could potentially be used to treat cancer epigenetically.

The fact that the cofactor is best bound to the active site inspired us to explore its interactions to LSD1/CoREST enzyme complex utilizing molecular dynamics simulation, which aids designing novel and potent inhibitors. Also, the conformational existence of the enzyme complex bound to the cofactor has been investigated. According to the molecular dynamics simulation study, LSD1/CoREST complex is present in open and closed conformations. Furthermore, tetrahydrofolate was found to bind to two binding subsites with different binding modes.

The model derived from the molecular dynamics simulation study and the key contacts to the active site were used in the subsequent structure based drug design and in silico screening, which revealed a number of new chemical entities with a potential inhibitory effect of LSD1/CoREST complex. In silico mining on National Cancer Institute (NCI) database identified 60 promising and structurally diverse inhibitors. The cytotoxic activities of these compounds were tested against different cancer cell lines with different expression modes of LSD1/CoREST complex such as leukaemia K562, prostate cancer PC3 and neuroblastoma SH-SY5Y. All compounds were also tested against normal fibroblast cells to study their selectivity against cancer cells.

Applying the abovementioned molecular modeling procedure yielded array of LSD1/CoREST inhibitors with IC₅₀ < 5 μM, when tested against different cancer cell lines. Three compounds inhibited the growth of PC3 prostate cells with IC₅₀ = (2.68, 2.08 and 2.95 μM), Four of them inhibited the growth of K562 leukaemia cells with IC₅₀ = (1.20, 1.92, 2.70, and 1.20 μM) and three of them inhibited the growth of SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cells with IC₅₀ = (0.27, 0.83 and 4.28 μM). These compounds are excellent candidates for further optimization.

Analysis of the impact of RB- Cannabidiol co-treatment on prostate cancer cells

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Abstract:

Prostate cancer (PCa) is the most commonly diagnosed urogenital cancers and cause of male cancer related deaths across the globe with Sub-Saharan African countries amongst those leading in high mortality rate. PCa is usually diagnosed at a later stage with the likelihood of resulting into metastatic ally advanced fatal stages which show clinical aggressiveness resulting in drug resistance. Therefore the use of phytochemicals such as those derived from Cannabis Sativa have shown improvements lately in research. Phyto-cannabinoids found in the plant have been proven to have potent anti-cancer activities. Cannabidiol (CBD), is a major non-psychoactive constituent of Cannabis Sativa, with various pharmacologic or putative medicinal properties such anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, and anti-tumour proliferative effects including induction of apoptosis. However, the precise molecular mechanism through which CBD mediates such effects is yet to be elucidated. The present study aimed to investigate the possible apoptotic and anti-proliferative mechanisms involved in the chemotherapeutic properties of Cannabidiol tin combination with targeted gene therapy.

Result: Cannabidiol inhibited cell proliferation in a dose-dependent manner, and 50% cell death was induced by 10.92 μ M. DNA fragmentation showed both smearing and laddering suggesting induction of apoptosis by the treatments. Microscopy has revealed morphological features of apoptosis in cells treated with CBD alone and in-combination with both p53 and siRB. The mode of cell death was further confirmed by an increase in the ratio of apoptosis relative to untreated cells, indicated by Annexin V/FITC staining. Caspase 3/7 activity assay confirmed an increase in apoptosis induction in co-treated cells with p53 and CBD as compared to siRB and p53 only treated cells. There was a significant increase in cell death in cells co-treated with p53 and CBD as compared to cells treated with SiRB only indicating the synergistic properties of the combinational therapy between p53 and CBD. qPCR analysis showed that RB knockdown increased the expression of CDK2 and RBBP6. Consequently, overexpression of P53 decreased their expression. These data suggest that Cannabidiol induced cell cycle arrest and apoptosis which may correlate with the re-expression of RB expression levels.

Conclusion: The findings in this study suggest that CBD has potential therapeutic properties that can be used in the treatment of prostate cancer in vitro. Silencing of RB gene leads to cancer proliferation and upregulation of p53 inhibits cell proliferation thus induce intrinsic caspase-dependent apoptosis. Combinational therapy between p53 and CBD could be a future therapeutic strategy for prostate cancer.

Keywords:

Cannabidiol, Prostate cancer, Apoptosis, combinatorial gene therapy, RT-qPCR, siRB, p53, DNA Fragmentation

Targeting DNA-interacting enzymes with a new class of DNA mimics

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Abstract:

Numerous essential biomolecular processes require the recognition of DNA surface features by proteins. Molecules mimicking these features could potentially act as decoys and interfere with pharmacologically or therapeutically relevant protein DNA interactions. Although naturally occurring DNA mimicking proteins have been described, synthetic tunable molecules that mimic the charge surface of double-stranded DNA are not known. Here, we report the design, synthesis and structural characterization of aromatic oligoamides that fold into single helical conformations and display a double helical array of negatively charged residues in positions that match the phosphate moieties in B-DNA. These molecules were able to inhibit several enzymes possessing non-sequence selective DNA-binding properties, including topoisomerase 1 and HIV-1 integrase, presumably through specific foldamer protein interactions, whereas sequence-selective enzymes were not inhibited. Such modular and synthetically accessible DNA mimics provide a versatile platform to design novel inhibitors of protein DNA interactions.

Predicting chemotherapeutic drug sensitivity by molecular, cellular and computational methods

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Abstract:

Precision cancer medicine, a modern therapeutic approach, is rapidly changing treatment strategies across cancer types. Oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) patients respond poorly to chemotherapy. Predicting anticancer drug response before the treatment of OSCC is a significant challenge. Recently, gene expression profiling and cell based assays reveals drug sensitivity that could be implemented for drug selection for patients. We analyzed the expression of 11 drug response related genes in 31 OSCC biopsies collected prior to any treatment, using custom designed PCR array. Further, we investigated drug response pattern of selected anticancer drugs using BH3 apoptotic profiling in the primary cells isolated from OSCC tissues. Then, we correlated the results of drug response gene expression pattern with apoptotic priming to predict tumor response to chemotherapy. The best performing drug (BPD) and response differences (RD) between the drugs were identified using statistical methods to select the best choice of drug in a personalized manner. Based on the Pierson correlation, we classified OSCC tumors as sensitive, moderately responsive or resistant to chemotherapy. We observed that 2 patients were resistant, 17 patients were moderately responsive and 12 patients were sensitive to chemotherapeutic drugs. We found that up-regulation of genes linked to drug resistance facilitates survival of tumor samples, which was revealed by the percentage of apoptotic priming. Moreover, we found that paclitaxel induced 40-45% apoptotic priming compared to other drugs. Average response difference (RD) analysis showed that 80% of tumors responded well to paclitaxel as compared to other other drugs studied that were less effective. Therefore, drug response gene expression pattern with the status of apoptotic priming in the tumor cells may be translated to the clinic and which will make a significant impact in cancer precision medicine.

Analgesics Prescribing Trends In Emergency And Out Patients At Skmch&Rc – A Cross Sectional Study

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Abstract:

Unnecessary or inappropriate prescription of analgesics specifically in emergency situation is a major concern. Sometimes inappropriate drugs are selected, like opioid use in first place not only cause serious side effects but also waste of precious drug in a country where availability of opioids is already in scarcity. Limited studies have examined the impact of analgesics prescribing trend in developing countries.

In our setting, we examined 5675 patients who visited emergency assessment room (EAR) or outpatient department (OPD) during the last 12 months and received different types of analgesics drugs for their pain management. Out of 5675 patient's prescription, there were only 105 prescriptions for morphine. This constitutes only 1.85 % of total prescriptions order out of 5675 physician orders. Moreover 3941 patients out of 5675 were managed with paracetamol plus tramadol combination. Nevertheless only 1629 patients received paracetamol & ibuprofen combination for their pain management. So from the above given prescription trend, we can say that if we evaluate the patients efficiently and prescribe analgesics according to pain scale, we can manage most of our patients without opioids. Proper analgesic prescribing will not only decrease opioids use but also decrease the suffering of patients.

Purpose of Study:

To review the rational use of analgesic prescribed in EAR and OPD

Time of Study:

12 month study (1st September 2017 to August 31st 2018)

Methods:

It was a retrospective cross sectional study and reviewed 5675 patients. Who were evaluated during the last one year during their visit in EAR or OPD for pain manage

Results:

Only 105 prescription having morphine as opioids prescribed to manage pain. Out of 5675 prescriptions orders, only 1.85 % were morphine based prescriptions. Efficient use of analgesic prescribing will not only decrease opioids use but also decrease the suffering of patients. We can further analyze the data in detail , by reviewing primary diagnosis, age , gender and pain scale to evaluate the effectiveness of analgesics drugs prescribed.

Conclusion:

Despite an oncology setup, the proportions of prescriptions having morphine were very small. Our findings support the need to further standardize and improve adherence to analgesic treatment guidelines.

Keywords:

Analgesic prescribing morphine, EAR, OPD

Increased recurrence rates of hepatocellular carcinoma after DAA therapy in a hepatitis C-infected Egyptian cohort: A comparative analysis

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Abstract:

In Egypt, hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) is the most common form of cancer and direct-acting antivirals (DAA) are administered on a large scale to patients with chronic HCV infection to reduce the risk. In this unique setting, we aimed to determine the association of DAA exposure with early phase HCC recurrence in patients with a history of HCV related liver cancer. This was a prospective cohort study of an HCV-infected population from one Egyptian specialized HCC management centre starting from the time of successful HCC intervention. The incidence rates of HCC recurrence between DAA-exposed and nonexposed patients were compared, starting from date of HCC complete radiological response and censoring after 2 years. DAA exposure was treated as time varying. Two Poisson regressions models were used to control for potential differences in the exposed and nonexposed group; multivariable adjustment and balancing using inverse probability of treatment weighting (IPTW). We included 116 patients: 53 treated with DAAs and 63 not treated with DAAs. There was 37.7% and 25.4% recurrence in each group after a median of 16.0 and 23.0 months of follow up, respectively. Poisson regression using IPTW demonstrated an association between DAAs and HCC recurrence with an incidence rate ratio of 3.83 (95% CI: 2.02-7.25), which was similar in the multivariable-adjusted model and various sensitivity analyses. These results add important evidence towards the possible role of DAAs in HCC reoccurrence and stress the need for further mechanistic studies and clinical trials to accurately confirm this role and to identify patient characteristics that may be associated with this event.

Keywords:

DAAs, Egypt, hepatitis c, hepatocellular carcinoma, recurrence